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HEALTH RISKS ASSESSMENT OF HEAVY METALS IN THREE PROCESSED LOCALLY CONSUMED SPICES FOR PHARMACEUTICAL APPLICATION

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Abstract

In this study, four (4) heavy metals were analyzed (Zn, Cu, Fe, Pb, and Na) using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) technique. Three (3) food spices namely processed curry powder; processed thyme and processed nutmeg were analyzed for these heavy metals. All the heavy metals analyzed were virtually found in all the spices at varied concentrations (0.135-0.188, 0.041-0.160, 0.311-1.224 and 0.021-0.368, mg/kg for Zn, Cu, Fe, and Pb, respectively) and ranged within the standards of WHO/FAO for metals in food spices. The result indicates that these food spices contain some mineral elements that are essential as nutraceuticals for the body. When these elements/nutrients are far above normal absorbable range, they possess a lot of health risk including questionable disorders. However, Health risk assessment result revealed that no health related issue may arise from its consumption since all the indicators (EDIM < 1; HRI < 1; THQ < 1 and HI < 1) were all less than unity. Therefore, the results showed that these spices can be useful in pharmaceutical applications since they contain appropriate amount of the studied heavy metals.